

Structural, magnetic and transport properties of $\text{CeAg}_{0.68}\text{Si}_{1.32}$ polycrystalline compound

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We report on a comprehensive study on the preparation, structure, magnetization, resistivity and heat capacity of the polycrystalline compound $\text{CeAg}_{0.68}\text{Si}_{1.32}$. The compound crystallizes in the hexagonal AlB_2 type structure with $P6/mmm$ space group. Magnetic susceptibility studies reveal two ferromagnetic transitions at 4.6 K and 7.6 K. A small hysteresis loop observed in isothermal magnetization at 2 K indicates a soft ferromagnetic behavior. Reduction in experimental value of saturation magnetization from the theoretical value is attributed to the Crystal Electric Field Effect (CEF). The temperature dependent specific heat capacity exhibits a broad hump at low temperatures (Fig. 1) which may be due to the bulk magnetic ordering. Resistivity data exhibits spin disorder scattering near the ordering temperature. The negative magnetoresistance (-3% at 2 K in 60 kOe) indicates ferromagnetic behavior.

Fig. 1. Temperature dependence of the heat capacity measured in different magnetic fields upto 90 kOe of $\text{CeAg}_{0.68}\text{Si}_{1.32}$.

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